

The Impact of Investments in Network Security on Business Performance

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Abstract

This paper examines the perception of information technology managers and chief information officer's regarding the importance of networks security to their organizations, and the impact of investments in networks security on business performance and whether additional investments in networks security would result in better organizational performance. The study examines large companies and small to mid-size companies, and concludes that CIO's perceive network security as an essential element in the well being of their organizations, and that IT managers perceives investments in networks security essentially as a priority, this view seems to be held more strongly by larger organizations than mid-size ones.

1. Introduction

Advances made in networking technology, explosive growth of the Internet, and the liberalization of telecommunication markets growingly causing modern business organization to reap the benefits of sophisticated networked computer applications. Unfortunately, the realization of these applications is often hampered by insecurities typical of open networks when messages can be intercepted and manipulated, the validity of documents can be denied, and personal data can be illicitly collected. Network security takes large share of organizational concern, budget, and effort. Organizations of all sizes realize today that networks security is essential to their existence therefore; management requires more security provided by IT personal with a shrinking budgets. As organizations become more dependants on networks communications, so do networks security becomes a major issue and an area of concern to organizations of all sizes world-wide. It is therefore important to explore management concerns regarding organizational performance, security concerns in one hand, and attempt to discover any correlations between networks security, investments, and organizational performance on the other.

2. Review of Literature

Networks security is an important issue at all organizations. However, it is largely ignored by chief

information officers and organizational upper management till problem occurred (Sisk, 2003). Most of the available literature concerning network security shows that most information technology managers agree on the importance of protecting their networks against security threats, although many are not willing to commit more investments to strengthen their networks against threats because of budgetary constraints (Gordon, and Muligan, 2002).

Smith (1999) argued that information technology security is highly related to small firm performance. Smith (1999) sampling of 150 small firms provided statistical significance that the greater the use of IT, the better they perform. Although his work did not show any statistical evidence of the direct relationship between network security and organizational performance, yet it showed that the importance of information technology to upper management is not directly linked to the performance of the organization. Empirical evidence provided then only shows that an increase the reliance on information technology to improve performance but not a reliance on network security specifically.

The issue of security discussed in available literature is only within the framework of information technology but not from the viewpoint of networks security. Kankanhalli et al (2003) asserts that information systems security is enjoying an increasing importance among small to mid-size, and large organizations and that security concerns are increasing among organizations is a world wide trend. Kankanhalli et al (2003) further asserts that there is an increasing concern that security threats can significantly harm organizational competitive position; however more support by management meant more preventive measures and more support to the internal information systems.

Kankanhalli et al (2003) also observed that financial institutions are more proactive in their security investments than other organizations. Given the nature of these institutions, management tends to understand that any violations in their networks security may cause loss of major market share, preach of client confidentiality, and loss of profitability.

Krause, (2003) makes a compelling argument as he describes organizational dilemma in terms of their desire to reduce cost to all departments including the IT department, and maintaining security and positive performance at the same time. Organizational problems becomes more complicated as their businesses becomes more global in nature and new network connections must be established with new business partners, suppliers, and customers.

Furthermore, Ratnasingam (2002) argue that networks security has a direct impact on organizational performance. This impact is evident in web-based businesses, which is forced to improve network security measures in order to maintain stable business operation, all in which reflects positively on organizational performance. Minden et al (1997) confirmed this argument early on by surveying various web-based and non web-based companies, their research also indicates that web-based businesses tend to have more investments in network security.

While both large and mid-size organizations equally understands that lack of adequate network security may jeopardize the assets of the organization, its functionality, and in many cases its existence, smaller organizations appears to be struggling in their network security investments largely because of the smaller budgets that allows whatever available funds to be allocated to other IT investments (Lei, 2003). Government organizations are no exception. A survey by Intelligent Decisions, found “77 percent of federal systems were certified and accredited as secure by October 2004, despite the administration's original goal to have 80 percent of systems secure by October 2003. In addition, 54 percent of agencies maintaining wireless networks did not have basic wireless security controls.” the Army Times (2005).

Symantec Corporation a leading antivirus and networks protection firm reported that the first half of 2005, Symantec observed more activity in sophisticated malicious code targeted at networks by being more focused, such malicious code exposed confidential information “threats also grew from an average of 2.99 million messages a day to 5.70 million between January 1 and June 30, 2005” Symantec (2005).

A research study co-released by the privacy research firm Ponemon Institute and the data security firm Vontu, supports the relationship issue between corporate network security and corporate performance, the 2005 benchmark study of corporate privacy

practices suggests “In a survey that polled 68 large companies with over 1,000 employees across all industries, 56 percent of respondents believe that safeguarding privacy has a direct positive impact on their company's brand or image in the marketplace. Seventy-nine percent of the polled companies have a separate privacy policy dedicated to employee information and 100 percent of the companies have a privacy policy for customer or consumer data, but only 80 percent have a privacy or data protection strategy. Budgets are still trying to catch up to an increased focus on privacy. Only 38 percent of the companies polled believe their resources are adequate to manage privacy requirements and only 31 percent have a formalized notification process in the event of a privacy breach.” Ponemon Institute, and Vontu (2005). The literature does not examine corporate profitability, yet it touches on corporate image, which is linked in many ways to corporate profitability.

Finally, Gartner research conducted a midsize enterprise summits in 2005, Browning (2006), which concluded that security topped all other corporate issues, and IT will continue to lead all other issues for midsize companies for the year 2006 in the U.S. and Canada. Browning further concludes that because of their smaller budgets, midsize businesses are not able to invest in the needed security areas “Midsize business security spending as a percentage of their overall IT budget was approximately 7 percent in 2005, with the majority of security spending ranging between 5 percent and 10 percent of their IT spending” Browning (2006).

3. Methodology

The main purpose of this section is to present the specific methodology procedures employed in testing the corporate CIO's perceptions. This section consists of several main items. The first item will deal with statement of problem. Then the research questions will be developed in the second section. The third section will be appropriated to the study's limitations. The sample and the questionnaire, which is considered to be the main tool for gathering data, will be discussed in the last item.

4. Statement of problem:

This paper attempt to determine the perception of information technology managers and chief information officers regarding:

*The importance of networks security.

*The impact of investments in networks security on business performance.

*And whether additional investments in networks security would result in better organizational performance.

5. Research Questions:

This study will attempt to answer the following questions:

1. Do organizations place any importance on networks security?
2. Does strong network security means better business performance?
3. Does lack of spending on network security impacts business performance?
4. Do additional investments in network security means improvement in business performance?
5. Is there a significant difference between mid-size and large organizations in terms of attention given to networks security?

6. Limitations of the Study:

This study examines only information technology managers and corporate CIO's perception of the importance of network security, investments in network security, and impact on business performance in mid-size and large organizations in the United States.

7. Sampling, questionnaire design, and data collection.

After defining the objectives of the study, samples had to be determined. The fieldwork was to cover as many organizations as possible in United States. The organizations in which the study covers are considered to be important to the stimulation of the economy in United States. The size of the organizations approached, ranging between mid-size to large organization of over 1000 employees. It is felt that network security studies probably required reasonable size organizations.

The questionnaire was designed to cover all variables included in this study. A survey was developed and consists of eight questions directly related to the organization network security, investments made, and management perception of business performance.

The survey was directed toward chief information officers or managers with equivalent responsibilities in charge of the IT department or overlooking investments in information systems. A list of over 500 emails of corporate chief information officers was

obtained from the Wall Street Journal, all 500 CIO were sent an email asking them to participate in the survey with complete description of the academic use of the data. In return, the results of the survey will be shared with participants so they can benefit from the results generated.

Questions of the survey was uploaded to special website provided by www.surveymonkey.com and all emails sent to participants included electronic link to the survey website to ease the process of participation in the survey, reduce cost and time since no mail is necessary, and simplifying the collection of data. Data collected from the survey was entered into statistical analysis software "SPSS", which is widely used by academics to run a variety of statistical analysis for academic use. The data analysis are then shown in tables and transferable from "SPSS" to word document.

8. Backgrounds of respondents and characteristics of organizations

Table (1) below represents a summary the background characteristics of the respondents and the organizations that participated in the study. It shows that 87% of the respondents were male business leaders in comparison to only 13% female business leaders. That result may be consistent with the controversial argument regarding the glass ceiling theory that promoting female to higher managerial positions is hindered by many difficulties. In term of age, the results revealed that the majority of respondents (69%) were over the age of 40 with an average age of 41 years. It may be argued that this age average reflects, to some extent, the maturity level of business leaders.

As far as length of services is concerned, the majority of respondent business leaders (73%) were business leaders whose length of service in the industry was more than 9 years with an average of 10 years, and (55%) were business leaders whose length of service in their companies was more than 9 years with an average of 8 years of service in the same companies. Also, the results of this study indicate that the average length of service for business leaders working in their current functional area of business is 6 years, whereas the average length of service for business leader at the current position is 5 years. Based on the previous results, one can notice that business leaders participated in this study have a considerable length of service either in their current position or in the industry in general.

Turning to the size of companies, analysis of the participants in the survey shows that out of 45 responses, 5 were large companies with over 1000 employees consisting of 11.1% of the total responses,

and 40 small to mid-size companies with less than 1000 employees consisting of 88.9% of the total responses Table:1.

Table 1: Summary of Respondent’s Backgrounds and Organization’s Sizes

Characteristic	Details	Frequencies	Average
Gender	Male	39	
	Female	6	
Age	Less than 30	1	41 year
	30-34	5	
	35-39	8	
	40-44	11	
	45and more	20	
Length of service in the industry	Less than 3	4	10 year
	3-5	3	
	6-8	5	
	9-11	8	
	12 and more	25	
Length of service in company	Less than 3	2	8 years
	3-5	10	
	6-8	8	
	9-11	11	
	12 and more	14	
Length of service in the current functional area	Less than 3	5	6 years
	3-5	8	
	6-8	9	
	9-11	7	
	12 and more	7	
Length of service in the current position	Less than 3	11	5 years
	3-5	16	
	6-8	9	
	9-11	5	
	12 and more	4	
Size of organization (Total number of employees)	Less than 100	3	723 employees
	100-499	21	
	500-999	16	
	1000 and more	5	

9. Data Analysis

Findings of the statistical analysis discussed below. All variables in the questionnaire were answered, no variable in all 45 questionnaires were missing, therefore, the study has 0 missing value.

In response to whether organizations utilize E commerce in achieving their tasks, the majority of the organizations (73%) indicated that E commerce is used in performing their activities (Table 2). This trend reflects the increasing importance of using the IT in different organizations.

Table 2: Factors affecting network security

Factors	Percentage agreeing / strongly agreeing	Percentage disagreeing / strongly disagreeing
Utilizing of e- commerce	73.3	26.7
emphases on network security	84.4	15.6
Investing money on network security	60	40
The impact of improving network security on organization's performance	91.1	8.9
More investment in network security is needed	84.4	15.6
More investment in network security will improve the overall business performance	84.2	17.8

In response to whether organizations place any importance on networks security, variable 3 of the questionnaire directly asked participants the following question; Do you think that your organization places high emphases on networks security? Table 2 showing above, 38 out of 45 agreed, this is 84.4% of the total companies surveyed answered positively, which indicates that's the vast majority of chief information officers or managers in charge of IT department thinks that their companies actually highly value networks security as a priority.

Additionally, 100% of large companies that consist of over 1000 employees answered yes to the question, confirming that the issue of network security is a high priority to large organizations. 60% only out of the total participants companies agreed that they invested enough money on network security, whereas 40% of these companies were admitted that the a mount of money invested on network security is not enough , they highlighted a critical situation caused by lack of investment on this important field (Table 2)

In response to another question of this study that is whether the participants companies think that improving the network security will positively impact the organization's performance , the vast majority of the participants companies (91% answered yes to the question, validating the believe within the majority of the organizations that is better networks security do actually lead to a better business performance. 100% of large companies with over 1000 employees answered yes to the question emphasizing the same understanding.

Furthermore, the question of whether more spending on network security is needed, also the majority of organizations with 84.4% agreeing that organizations

need to invest more money on networking. It is believed that more investment will lead to have better network security which intern lead to better organizational performance

The last question of whether additional investments in network security means improvement in business performance was answered by the above table (Table 2), were 82.2% answered yes, asserting that additional investments in networks security will improve business performance. 100% of large companies with over 1000 employees answered that yes additional investments are required and will improve business performance

This study attempts to determine is whether a significant difference between mid-size and large organizations exists in terms of importance given to networks security. Analysis shows that there is a significant difference exists in terms of responses provided by large organizations and mid-size ones. 100% of large organizations agree that more investments are needed in networks security, and that more investments mean better business performance from information technology managers' point of view. On the other hand, over 84% of mid-size companies seem to confirm the same argument. This could be attributed to number of factors.

Although we had analyzed the respondent's responses by using the frequencies, it is worthwhile looking at correlation coefficients between these variables to investigate their relationships and how they related to each other. Results indicate that companies' sizes have no relationship with other variables (Table 3). However Pearson's correlation test has shown a strong and positive relationship between utilizing e-commerce and other variables. It is believed that

utilizing e-commerce leads to place high emphases on network security as $r = 0.712$ and $p < 0.001$ ¹. On the same line the chief executive officers pointed out that utilizing e-commerce could increase the amount of money need to be invested on network security as $r = .739$, $.712$ and $p < 0.001$.The respondents stressed that utilizing e-commerce will impact positively the overall business performance as $r = .518$, $.771$ and $p < 0.001$.

Moreover, Pearson's correlation test has revealed a strong relationship between placing high emphases on network security and other variables as listed in Table 8 (organization's performance ,more investment needed, and the improvement of the overall business performance as $r = .728$, 1.00 , $.923$ and $p < 0.001$. In addition, such a correlation has confirmed that investing enough money may lead to improve

network security, increase the investment level needed , and improve the organization's performance and as $r = .382$, $.526$, $.569$ and $p < 0.001$. On other hand, it was also found that improving network security could increase the level of investment needed which in turn lead to increase the overall organization's performance as $r = .728$, $.672$ and $p < 0.001$. Lastly, results of the correlation test have indicated that the significant and the positive relationship between the level of investment needed on network security, and the overall organization's performance as $r = .923$ and $p < 0.001$. It has been approved that increase in the level of investment, will impact the performance of the organization positively. This important result support the trend indicated earlier by previous research conducted by Ratnasingam (2002) and Kankanhalli *et al* (2003).

Table 3: Correlation matrix among variables for the responses of top managers in American organizations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1.Size of companies	1						
2.Utilizing E commerce	.213	1					
3.Emphases on network security	.152	.712**	1				
4.Investing enough money	.289	.739**	.526**	1			
5.Improving network security	.110	.518**	.728**	.382**	1		
6.Investment needed	.152	.712**	1.00**	.526**	.728**	1	
7.Business performance	.164	.771**	.923*	.569**	.672**	.923**	1

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

10. Conclusion

In conclusion, IT managers and Chief Information Officers (CIO’s) perceive network security as an essential element in the well being of their organizations, which confirms Kankanhalli et al (2003) argument. Furthermore, IT managers perceive investments in networks security essential and a priority. This view seems to be held more strongly by larger organizations than mid-size ones. One interpretation is that the volume of business transactions in large organizations requires more advanced networks security. The same reason also leads to believe that large organizations enjoy larger budgets where they can afford more investments in networks security.

Large business volume and transaction especially in the financial sector can justify large investment in business networks security, to maintain efficient flow of business operation, flow of information, and to sustain competitive advantage, which corresponds with

the conclusion of Ponemon Institute, and Vontu (2005). Another interpretation as to why IT managers in large organizations perceive more investments in networks security is highly needed, is the fact that IT departments tends to enjoy large budgets, and maintaining these large budgets is a priority to most CIO’s. Small to mid-size companies however, has more limited budgets and can not invest more than they should in improving networks. In fact, 15.6% of the surveyed companies indicated that no additional investments are needed in their networks security, while 100% of large companies indicated that more investments are needed.

The research also concludes that more investments in networks security is highly needed in all organization. Investments in networks security will provide higher protection from the increasing attacks on corporate data, and client’s information. More investments will inevitably shield corporate networks from losing information, which is the essence of business today, provides more secured environment for business

transactions, maintain data integrity, and increases efficiency for cross business operations.

11. Further Research

Further research is needed with larger participation of large companies and an inclusion of smaller size companies as well. Further research of the IT departments in the financial industry will help develop this topic further.

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